

tunES

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D1.1 REPORT ON BUILDING BLOCK EVENT

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Abstract: This report summarises the objectives, key discussions, and outcomes of the tunES event ‘Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges’.

REVISION HISTORY

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AEA	Austrian Energy Agency
EC	European Commission
ENEA	Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The tunES project organised an event ‘Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges’ on the 22nd of May, 2024 in Brussels and online. The core target group were energy agencies and ministries as well as supporting organisations.

The event was initially planned for month four (M4) of the project (December 2023). It has been agreed with the policy advisor to defer the event to month nine (M9) due to the ongoing negotiations on the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) and collision with other important events for DG ENER.

Given the importance of stakeholder engagement and the promotion of collaborative learning, the event was structured as a hybrid meeting. This format ensured wide participation, accommodating both in-person and online attendees, thus maximising the impact and reach of the discussions.

This report, D1.1 "Report on Building Block Event", aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the objectives, key discussions, and outcomes of this event. Through this documentation, the report captures the essence of the collaborative efforts undertaken during the tunES event and outlines the strategic directions and insights gained as the tunES project moves forward in its mission to optimise energy efficiency instruments across Europe.

2 Objectives

The tunES event ‘Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges’ was aimed to gather diverse stakeholders to facilitate the exchange between energy agencies and external followers. The core target group of the event were national energy agencies, organisations supporting agencies and by extension ministries.

tunES identified the following multiple objectives of the event:

- provide Member States with means to transpose the EPBD recast with impact
- offer introduction on tunES key outputs and the Better Regulation method
- give room to horizontally replicable results (i.e. useful for Member States)
- invite Member States to follow tunES and maybe apply some of our methods.

3 Organisation

The tunES event ‘Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges’ was carefully planned and organised by ENEA as a WP1 leader.

Originally, the event was foreseen as an evidence collection workshop in December 2023. The event was moved due to collisions with other EC / CINEA events. Another approach in early January was moved due to final negotiations of the EPBD. All changes occurred in agreement with the Granting Authority.

Ultimately, the event was scheduled for the 22nd of May, 2024 as a part of the series of events organised by CINEA buildings cluster (21st – 22nd of May) and Horizon 2020 projects (23rd of May) in Brussels.

The strategic choice of a hybrid format of the event helped to maximise participation, allowing stakeholders from across Europe to engage, irrespective of their geographical location or constraints. The on-site part of the event was organised in Brussels, Belgium, at the location for meetings ‘Comet Louise’ that allowed the room for up to 50 participants. The online stream

of the event was ensured by using the Microsoft Teams webinar link. The event was not recorded.

3.1 Dissemination of the event

tunES project used various means of communication in order to announce the upcoming event and attract wider audience.

Targets group

Dissemination of the event was built on the speaker and target group research conducted on the early stages of preparation for the original event in December. The list of stakeholders included about 70 people from various organisations such as national and regional energy agencies, ministries, associations of professionals as well as research centres and industry.

Communication channels

Communication was conducted by the project and by each organisation, energy agencies in particular.

Firstly, several informative posts were created in project's LinkedIn and Mastodon accounts in social media. The tunES consortium members actively shared the posts to attract attention of national interested parties and project followers (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. LinkedIn post announcing the event

Secondly, tunES and energy agencies sent out several targeted newsletters in English and national languages (Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4). The recipients of the newsletters included people subscribed to the newsletters via the form on tunES website (<https://empirica.com/tunes/newsletter/>) and the stakeholders identified by energy agencies. Additionally, personal emails were sent and phone calls done by the tunES consortium members to inform and invite the stakeholders already showing their interest in the tunES project.

Figure 2. Newsletter with invitation to register for the event

tunES invites to participate in Survey and attend EPC&SRI events

Dear Tatiana,

We are glad to inform you that the tunES project has some important news to share.

Your input is crucial for shaping the future of building certification tools and techniques in Europe.

<https://emp.onl/tunes-survey>

Survey

tunES launched a **survey on future of EPC and SRI**. It is part of the data collection to fully understand the current national situation, identify problems, and design suitable and impactful policy measures. Please fill the survey: [EUSurvey - Survey \(europa.eu\)](#). It will take less than 15 minutes.

Event

We are organising a hybrid event on **22 May, 2024** titled ***Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges.***

The aims of the tunES event are to

- share and discuss the existing practices for EPC and SRI as starting points for national implementation
- explain the tunES policy approach in applying Better Regulation Guidelines invite interested parties to become a follower
- share and discuss useful tools by other projects to test SRI and (nationally) new EPC elements
- connect stakeholders to facilitate an ambitious and smooth national implementation

Registration link: <https://emp.onl/tunES-event>

Figure 3. ENEA Energy Efficiency Department Newsletter with invitation to register for the event¹

Vi segnaliamo

Il progetto tunES organizza l'evento "Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges"

14 Maggio 2024

Nell'ambito del progetto europeo **tunES**, finanziato dal programma LIFE 2022, che vede la partecipazione di **ENEA** insieme alle Agenzie per l'Energia di altri sei Stati Membri, il prossimo 22 maggio a Bruxelles si svolgerà l'evento **Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges** in modalità ibrida.

L'evento, introdotto da ENEA, sarà l'occasione per condividere e discutere le pratiche esistenti su temi dell'**Attestato di Prestazione Energetica (EPC)** e lo **Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)** e le relative novità nella revisione della **Direttiva sulla Prestazione Energetica nell'edilizia (EPBD)** recentemente pubblicata sulla gazzetta ufficiale dell'Unione Europea.

L'agenda prevede un intervento di **EMPIRICA**, coordinatore del progetto, che illustrerà l'approccio di tunES al fine di definire policies e percorsi che facilitino l'adozione di buone pratiche in ambito EPC e SRI a livello nazionale, seguendo i cinque blocchi tematici: *Comprendere l'EPC, Aggiornare l'EPC, Database e strumenti di calcolo, Sviluppo e diffusione dello SRI, Integrazione degli strumenti EPC e SRI*. In questo contesto, ENEA presenterà un'attenta analisi dell'attuale stato dell'EPC in Italia.

L'evento vedrà, inoltre, la partecipazione di referenti di alcuni progetti europei per condividere e discutere strumenti utili per testare l'SRI e aggiornare l'EPC.

È possibile partecipare online all'evento previa registrazione al seguente [LINK](#)

L'invito è aperto a tutti gli stakeholder del settore, enti di ricerca, referenti di progetti sulle tematiche affrontate e istituzioni.

Per maggiori informazioni: <https://tunes-project.eu>

Referenti: **Biagio Di Pietra** (biagio.dipietra@enea.it), **Luca La Notte** (luca.lanotte@enea.it), **Alessandro Lorenzo Palma** (alessandrolorenzo.palma@enea.it) - Dipartimento Unità Efficienza Energetica ENEA

A seguire, il 23 Maggio si svolgerà l'evento **The Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates Conference EPBD Recast Edition**, anch'esso in modalità ibrida. Partendo dai risultati di quattro progetti Horizon (**crossCert**, **EPC RECAST**, **EUB SuperHub** e **iBRoad2EPC**) e dalla panoramica del contesto europeo, verrà approfondita la tematica dell'EPC con un particolare riferimento alla nuova EPBD.

È possibile partecipare online all'evento previa registrazione al seguente [LINK](#)

Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges

22 May, 2024
14:00 - 18:00 (CEST)

¹ <https://lc.cx/G6lzhS>

Figure 4. ENEA Italia in classe A Newsletter² with invitation to register for the event³

The image shows a screenshot of an email newsletter from ENEA Italia in classe A. The header includes logos for 'Italia in classe A', 'Università del Piemonte Orientale', 'ENEA', and 'Agenzia Nazionale Efficienza Energetica'. The main heading reads: 'Il progetto tunES organizza l'evento "Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges"'. Below this is a graphic with the text 'Tuning EPC and SRI instruments to deliver full potential' and the 'tunES' logo. The event details are: '22 May, 2024, 14:00 - 18:00 (CEST)'. The body of the newsletter contains the following text:

Nell'ambito del progetto europeo tunES, finanziato dal programma LIFE 2022, che vede la partecipazione di ENEA insieme alle Agenzie per l'Energia di altri sei Stati Membri, il prossimo 22 maggio a Bruxelles si svolgerà l'evento Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges in modalità ibrida.

L'evento, introdotto da ENEA, sarà l'occasione per condividere e discutere le pratiche esistenti su temi dell'Attestato di Prestazione Energetica (EPC) e lo Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) e le relative novità nella revisione della Direttiva sulla Prestazione Energetica nell'edilizia (EPBD) recentemente pubblicata sulla Gazzetta ufficiale dell'Unione Europea.

L'agenda prevede un intervento di EMPIRICA, coordinatore del progetto, che illustrerà l'approccio di tunES al fine di definire policies e percorsi che facilitino l'adozione di buone pratiche in ambito EPC e SRI a livello nazionale, seguendo i cinque blocchi tematici: Comprendere l'EPC, Aggiornare l'EPC, Database e strumenti di calcolo, Sviluppo e diffusione dello SRI, Integrazione degli strumenti EPC e SRI. In questo contesto, ENEA presenterà un'attenta analisi dell'attuale stato dell'EPC in Italia.

L'evento vedrà, inoltre, la partecipazione di referenti di alcuni progetti europei per condividere e discutere strumenti utili per testare l'SRI e aggiornare l'EPC.

È possibile partecipare online all'evento previa registrazione al seguente [LINK](#)

L'invito è aperto a tutti gli stakeholder del settore, enti di ricerca, referenti di progetti sulle tematiche affrontate e istituzioni.

Per maggiori informazioni: <https://tunes-project.eu>

Referenti: Biagio Di Pietra (biagio.dipietra@enea.it), Luca La Notte (luca.lanotte@enea.it), Alessandro Lorenzo Palma (alessandrolorenzo.palma@enea.it) - Dipartimento Unità Efficienza Energetica ENEA

A seguire, il 23 Maggio si svolgerà l'evento The Next Generation Energy Performance Certificates Conference EPBD Recast Edition, anch'esso in modalità ibrida. Partendo dai risultati di quattro progetti Horizon (crossCert, EPC RECAST, EUB SuperHub e iBRoad2EPC) e dalla panoramica del contesto europeo, verrà approfondita la tematica dell'EPC con un particolare riferimento alla nuova EPBD.

È possibile partecipare online all'evento previa registrazione al seguente [LINK](#)

² <https://lc.cx/G6lzhS>³ <https://lc.cx/5SqX4W>

4 Event

4.1 Agenda and speakers

The time and duration of the event were limited due to its position in the series of events. Following the event organised by the CINEA buildings cluster, tunES event began in the afternoon and lasted for four hours with the following time for networking.

The agenda used for the presentation was as shown in Table 1. The event was divided into two sections separated by a short break. The first part was dedicated to the horizontal introduction by CINEA of the EPBD recast and activities in the field as well as the presentation of tunES approach and main project's outcomes. The second part consisted of the presentations given by invited speakers from different EU projects working in the EPC and SRI domain.

Table 1. Agenda of the event

22 May 2024		
14:00-14:30	Reception	
14:30-14:40	Welcome and Introduction	ENEA
14:40-14:55	Summary EPBD recast of EPC and SRI	CINEA/ENER
14:55-15:10	EnR Activity in EPBD	EnR
15:10-15:30	Building Blocks and Practice collection+ Q&A	EMPIRICA
15:30-15:50	tunES approach, BRG Guidance and Follower invite	EMPIRICA
15:50-16:10	Exemplary Problem Trees presented by energy agencies	ENEA & AEA
16:10-16:30	Break	
16:30-16:45	SRI Support Action: offers and steps coming	VITO
16:45-17:00	SRI online calculation tool	SRI2Market
17:00-17:15	Research results on integration of SRI/EPC evidence	iEBD
17:15-17:30	Hub for advanced digital tools for EPC & SRI professionals	SMARTEREP
17:30-17:45	Closing remarks and next steps	EMPIRICA
18:00-19:30	Afterwork networking with drinks	

During the first part of the event, the tunES consortium members, ENEA and empirica, gave the introduction to the event, presented tunES approach, Practice Collection, and BRG Guidance. Two Energy Agencies (ENEA and AEA) shared their examples of national current Problem Trees on EPC.

In the second part, several external speakers were invited to develop the discussion on EPC and SRI and share their findings and actions in the field of energy performance of buildings:

- João Cleto (ADENA) presented EnR Building Working Group activities and plans in EPBD as well as the SRI2MARKET assessment tool
- Katarina Kosutova (VITO) shared the support actions provided by the SRI support team
- Andrei Vladimir Litui (EPB Center/REHVA) showed the results on integration of SRI, EPC and other tools

- Sara Momi (R2M Solution) presented the SmarterEPC Hub for EPC and SRI professionals.

4.2 Participants

During the preparation phase, tunES identified that the target group of the event were primarily national energy agencies, organisations supporting agencies, and ministries. Representatives of CINEA and other EU projects were also invited to share their findings and experience in the field of EPC and SRI.

Considering the participants of the tunES event, 110 people registered in the online registration form (Figure 5), of whom 89 attended the event online and 26 were present in Brussels in person, resulting in a very high participation rate. Some participants were invited to join the tunES event ‘Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges’ after the CINEA building cluster event, which was held earlier in the same room.

Figure 5. Event registration page

The screenshot shows the event registration page for 'Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges'. The header features the event title in large blue text, the date '22 May, 2024', and the time '14:00 - 18:00 (CEST)'. Logos for the European Union and 'Funded by the European Union' are visible. Below the header, the event title is repeated with the tunES logo. The main content area is divided into sections: 'Details', 'Event objectives', and 'Location in Brussels'. A 'Register' button is present, but it is greyed out with the message 'This event has passed.'.

Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges

22 May, 2024
14:00 - 18:00 (CEST)

tunES - Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges

Details

The tunES project is organising a hybrid event on 22 May, 2024 at 14:00-18:00 followed by afterwork networking until 19:30. The event will take place in Brussels and online.

The mission of tunES is to prepare national implementation of Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) and integrate it with the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) with 7 national Energy Agencies following the methodology provided by the Better Regulation Guideline. Currently, the project is collecting evidence on existing EPC and SRI practices and making first steps towards the development of national policy options by identifying pressing problems with the current implementation.

Event objectives

The event aims at

- National energy agencies and ministries
- Projects in the EPC and SRI domain
- It remains open to the public

The aim of the tunES event are to

- share and discuss the existing practices for EPC and SRI as starting points for national implementation
- explain the tunES policy approach in applying Better Regulation Guidelines invite interested parties to become a follower
- share and discuss useful tools by other projects to test SRI and (nationally) new EPC elements
- connect stakeholders to facilitate an ambitious and smooth national implementation

The participant number in Brussels will be limited. Energy agencies and ministries will be given priority with remaining spaces to be distributed. **We will confirm physical participation by beginning of May.** You can still attend online.

Location in Brussels: COMET, Place Stéphanie 20, 1050 Brussels

This event has passed.

Details

- 📅 Wed, May 22
- 🕒 2:00 PM - 6:00 PM GMT+2
- 📍 Online event

Register

The profile of the participants has covered a wide spectrum of stakeholders:

- multiple European energy agencies and ministries (Austria, Greece, Croatia, Poland, Germany, Portugal, Bulgaria, Slovakia, Hungary)
- researchers from numerous universities (Poland, Austria, Bulgaria, Germany, Italy, Spain)
- associations of professionals and business representatives (Canada, Austria, Portugal, Poland)
- representatives of various EU projects.

5 Results of the event

As the result, the event organised by tunES has achieved the set objectives. tunES and invited speakers presented the current activities in the EPC and SRI domain in the EU. Engaged participants took part in the discussions on EPC and SRI which provided insights into the ways to overcome national challenges in energy performance and support actions.

tunES presented the key outcomes of the project and the methodology providing examples of national Problem Trees and Practice Collection. This helped to attract attention to the project and gain new followers. Member States received useful information on methods and tools that could be replicable and used in their situation.

APPENDIX I: PRESENTATION FOR THE EVENT

The PowerPoint Presentation of the event ‘Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges’ organised by the tunES project on the 22nd of May, 2024 is available online: <https://emp.onl/tunes-presentation>.

Tuning EPC and SRI. Practices and methods to analyse national challenges | Agenda tunES 4

Agenda

14:30-14:45	Welcome and Introduction	ENEA	
14:45-14:55	Welcme from CINEA	CINEA	
14:55-15:10	EnR Activity in EBPD	EnR/ADENE	
15:10-15:30	Building Blocks and Practice collection	EMPIRICA	
15:30-15:50	tunES approach, BRG Guidance and Follower invite	EMPIRICA	
15:50-16:10	Exemplary Problem Trees presented by energy agencies	ENEA & AEA	
16:10-16:30	Break		
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